

HIGH TEMPERATURES WHEN USING ASLT UNDERESTIMATE THE SHELF LIFE OF FOOD

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The issue of the shelf life of food systems is not only a technical, but also a global environmental problem. The widely used ASLT (Accelerated Shelf Life Testing) method for food, feed, and medicines requires verification of the validity of its temperature conditions, including when it comes to hardware solutions that allow automated forecasting of shelf life. To verify the adequacy of the estimates, both machine learning algorithms for reanalysis of data published in the literature and proprietary data obtained using IR Fourier spectrometry during semi-annual aging of samples were used. It has been shown that the recommended conditions for ASLT at temperatures of 70–100 °C and above only save analysis time, and are more suitable for assessing the stability of non-food samples (for example, gasoline) than for food.

Keywords: Accelerated shelf life test (ASLT); underestimation of values; IR-spectrometry of food oils; oxidation of food; activation energy of chemical reactions (E_a); artificial neural network.

Introduction. According to current United Nations reports and work carried out by international research teams, slightly more than 1/3 of all products and food raw materials are lost annually, thereby contributing to food waste volume [1, 2], a phenomenon associated with significant environmental risks and anthropogenic impact on the ecosystem. As has been demonstrated, when solving this global problem, the role of an adequate assessment of the shelf life of food products is extremely important [2]. All this takes the topic of food shelf life from a purely technical level to a global ecological and economic level.

For this reason, research in the field of food system stability is one of the important areas of modern food science [3], including in connection with understanding the relationship of these processes with the ability to resist the oxidative influence of free radicals. For these purposes, various physicochemical methods are most often used, such as spectrometry and mass spectrometry [4, 5], as well as colorimetry in the visible and UV spectra. The latter is used, for example, to determine the rate of oxidation processes by measuring anisidine [6] and iodine numbers [7]. Other common approaches include acid number determination [8], IR spectroscopy [9, 10], and chromatographic methods for analyzing changes in chemical composition [11].

Chemical degradation products of lipids and other components of food systems can be toxic to humans or impair the organoleptic properties of food [12, 13]. Taking this into account is important both for the engineering of new food products and for understanding post-production processes that are influenced by environmental parameters. For this reason, scientific areas related to shelf life determination (commodity science), storage conditions (environmental and logistical tasks), and the ability of food systems to preserve their chemical composition over time (food chemistry) remain quite relevant [3]. However, it is not always possible to conduct long-term experiments to assess shelf life in natural conditions, primarily due to the complexity of controlling environmental parameters [14]. This has led to a proliferation of accelerated aging methods, known collectively as the *Accelerated Shelf Life Test* (ASLT) [14–16].

ASLT methods are based on the now-well-known Arrhenius equation (Equation 1), which correlates with the empirical Van't Hoff rule. This rule describes a two- to four- fold increase in the rate of chemical reactions for every 10 °C rise in the temperature of the reaction medium.

$$K = Ae^{-E_A/RT}, \quad (1)$$

Where K – is the rate of the chemical reaction, A is the pre-exponential factor, E_A is the activation energy of joules per mole, R is the universal gas constant equal to $8,314 \text{ J} \times \text{mol}^{-1} \times \text{K}^{-1}$, and T is the temperature in kelvin.

A number of authors suggest the use of other mathematical models. Nevertheless, checking the adequacy of each requires independent research [3, 15, 16]. Various ASLT protocols have now been developed, the essence of which is to increase the temperature and analyze the exposure time of a food product under specified conditions.

The exposure time at elevated temperatures is measured until complete or partial rancidity occurs (e.g., in oils). The resulting shelf life, typically expressed in hours, is then recalculated to normal storage conditions ($20\text{--}25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, atmospheric pressure). Based on such physicochemical principles, analytical devices such as Oxitest or Rancimat have been developed to estimate shelf life. Some of these devices resemble those used to assess the stability of gasoline and other fuels for internal combustion engines. For example, RapidOxy allows the use of increased oxidizer gas pressure ($6\text{--}8 \text{ atm}$) during analysis. Given that food systems consist of both stable and labile components a fact that affects the estimates-questions arise regarding the appropriateness of such physical conditions for analyzing food systems.

In their experiments, researchers seek to reduce exposure time as much as possible and choose very high temperature ranges (from 80°C upward). At the same time, it is known that reaction temperature affects not only the reaction rate but also, according to *collision theory*, increases collision energy. This leads to overcoming intermolecular resistance and active oxidation of structures that remain stable under normal conditions [17]. As a result, at elevated temperatures, the likelihood of spontaneous oxidative reactions increases, regardless of whether the fatty acids in the sample are saturated or unsaturated.

A similar methodological problem concerns the justification for increasing pressure in ASLT (it is assumed that this may reduce data scatter). A more reasonable explanation is that pressure increases during experiments because gas solubility decreases with rising temperature [18, 19]. Such conditions affect the rate of oxidant diffusion, the speed and frequency of particle collisions, and ultimately the results obtained.

At the same time, independent assessments would be preferable. However, the difficulties of such work arise from the known variability in food product composition (due to «ecological and geographical zoning» of raw materials) and from differences in analytical conditions across research groups. In our opinion, an elegant solution is to reanalyze already published data obtained using hardware solutions (e.g., Oxitest), especially since machine learning algorithms make this approach relatively easy to implement.

Thus, this **work aimed** to reanalyze data from previously published studies using neural networks and to predict previously unpublished values obtained with automated hardware solutions (Oxitest analyzer).

Materials and methods. The materials for the study were published data [19] on the chemical composition and oxidation rate of 10 types of freshly squeezed vegetable oils (sesame, linseed, pecan, sunflower), as well as their fatty acid ratios. Oxidation rates at different temperatures for each fatty acid composition and predicted storage values at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were also taken from the same publication. All published data were entered into a table we compiled, which was used to train an artificial neural network (hereinafter, ANN).

The ANN structure was chosen in the form of a multilayer perceptron. Figure 1 shows a schematic description of the neural network architecture.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the neural network architecture (ANN). Note: Part of the input and hidden layer neurons are not shown. A shared neuron is indicated in the output layer, since the same structure was used to calculate two values: IP (induction point) — the time in hours before the onset of uncontrolled oxidation — and SL (shelf life) in days. BpS is a bipolar sigmoid function. Numbers in green circles (e.g., 14:0) represent fatty acid concentrations; X1 and T2 represent physical parameters such as temperature, antioxidant concentrations, etc.

This structure was dictated by the conventional nature and relative simplicity of our calculations, similar to approaches in the literature [20]. According to the publication [19], the authors found linear relationships between the predicted shelf life of oils and the conditions under which ASLT was conducted, which allowed the use of relatively compact ANN architectures. The input neurons (21 in total) contained data on fatty acid composition, analysis temperature, inflection time on the graph (known as the induction point, IP) during uncontrolled oil oxidation, the proportion of unsaturated, polyunsaturated, and monounsaturated fatty acids, iodine number, smoking point, and the proportions of carotenoids, chlorophylls, and tocopherols, measured at different analysis temperatures (70 °C, 90 °C, and 100 °C).

The hidden layer contained no more than five neurons, with a bipolar sigmoid function serving as the activation function. Using this structure, two IP values were predicted — the induction time (in hours) before the inflection on the graph at different temperatures, and the predicted storage time in days (shelf life, SL). All correlations were assessed using Pearson's correlation coefficient and Tukey's test. The data were processed in Excel. Graphs and statistical analyses were performed using Statistica 10 and PAST. The graphs were processed in Corel Draw.

The second block of data for comparison consisted of results obtained for six types of vegetable oils: linseed, sunflower, coconut, olive, and corn, as well as a blend of these five oils in equal proportions. These were analyzed using an IR-Fourier spectrophotometer. The analyses were performed on a Bruker Alpha spectrophotometer equipped with an attenuated total reflection (ATR) accessory. For each of the listed samples, parameters were measured repeatedly: in their native state, after 4 hours of heating at 90 °C, and after six months of open storage in a dark room (with access to oxygen, open container) at 20 °C. All values were normalized and averaged. Changes in the spectral curves were then analyzed in comparison with known data on the influence of emerging and disappearing molecular groups on spectral characteristics.

Results and discussions. Recent evidence suggests that the Van't Hoff empirical rule is not strictly linear over the 20–100 °C temperature range [3]. However, even if we accept the

linear nature of correlations and mathematical models based on the Arrhenius equation, many researchers still neglect the role of activation energy (E_a). As is well known, activation energy is linked to the other parameters shown in Equation 1.

Using a neural network, we predicted the missing values for 40, 50, 60 and 80 °C (these data were missing in the original work), so we obtained a continuous series of values in 10 °C increments from 40 to 100 °C.

To predict the values, three points were selected (according to the algorithm from the published work). The entire range was divided into three partially overlapping ranges: the low-temperature range (40–50–60 °C, average 50 °C), the moderate-temperature range (50–60–80 °C, average 63,3 °C), and the high-temperature range (70–90–100 °C, average 86,6 °C). The final predicted values (in storage days) with 95 % confidence intervals (CI) are shown in Figure 2. Thus, the predicted values depend on the analysis temperature (i.e., the selected reference points).

For example, the predicted shelf life values obtained for the 70–100 °C range are statistically different from those for other temperature ranges (their 95 % CIs do not overlap). In our opinion, such low estimates arise because activation energy increases significantly with temperature. Moreover, under elevated pressure, these conditions enable oxygen to oxidize both unsaturated and saturated fatty acids, which on average leads to a drop in predicted shelf life values.

Figure 2. Predicted storage values (in days) with 95% confidence intervals (ordinate axis) for 10 types of vegetable oils across three temperature ranges (color-coded). The middle line within each rectangle indicates the mean value. Note: Values for the 70–100 °C range are from the literature; all other values were predicted using an ANN.

In this regard, a number of recent studies conducted without considering this factor at temperatures of 80–120 °C and above seem controversial [15, 19]. This approach is most likely justified for assessing the stability of distillates or fuels and lubricants for internal combustion engines, as suggested by American and European standards (ASTM D7525-14-

2024; EN 16091:2022). However, gasoline and other fuels consist of substances with similar chemical structures, which is not the case for vegetable oils or other food systems. They are mixtures of saturated and unsaturated structures that can differ by a factor of two in carbon skeleton length, among other differences.

Returning to Figure 2, we find that the values for the 40–60 °C range are overestimated relative to the average. The opposite is true: as temperature decreases, so do oxidative processes and activation energy, while the differences in predicted values increase. This logic can be extended further: as temperatures approach absolute zero, oxidation processes slow down so much that they would be expected to cease entirely at absolute zero. If research were conducted at such low temperatures, shelf life estimates would be overestimated, regardless of the food product's chemical composition. Conversely, at excessively high temperatures, all food storage periods are underestimated.

At both extremely high and low temperatures, not only the mean values are distorted but also the spread of estimates (sigma). This indicates the poor statistical power of such data to distinguish samples by shelf life. The largest range of values occurs in the 50–80 °C range, suggesting that this range provides the greatest discriminatory power and, consequently, the highest sensitivity of the method.

Based on the values obtained, we calculated the deviation (sigma) of the predicted induction point (IP) values relative to the mean. The graph is shown in Figure 3. As shown, the maximum deviation occurs at approximately 58 °C (this point represents the average value for the entire range). However, for the calculated values in the 40–100 °C range, the maximum spread — and therefore the sensitivity of the method — shifts slightly to approximately 66,5 °C, with a 95 % CI of 61–72 °C.

Figure 3. The spread of 95 % CI values (relative to the mean) for literature-based and modeled estimates, along with the corresponding trend lines (dotted). Note: The multi-colored lines correspond to IP values for samples obtained at different temperatures. The average values for ANN-predicted samples correspond to point A (approximately 66,5 °C). The average values based on graphical analysis of the entire data range are indicated by point B (approximately 58 °C). The 95 % CI for the forecast data is highlighted by two red dotted lines to the left and right of point A, corresponding to temperatures of approximately 61–72 °C. The intersection point labeled C indicates where the trend lines of the two data series cross (and corresponds to temperatures below 0 °C).

The IP calculations (Figure 3) suggest that ASLT shelf life estimates at temperatures outside the 53–72 °C range are either overestimated or underestimated. This range represents the maximum spread after subtracting the 95 % CI values for the average point (58 °C). The direction of the bias depends on whether the temperature is below or above this interval.

The sensitivity of the method decreases beyond this 95 % confidence interval. The use of high temperatures would be justified only if fats consisted of a single substance or of substances with similar physicochemical parameters. However, as mentioned earlier, food systems are multicomponent, which greatly distorts the values in such temperature ranges.

Notably, an earlier study – albeit using older methods – reached conclusions similar to ours [14, 17], though with a caveat regarding polyunsaturated fatty acids. The authors noted that if a sample has a high omega-3 fatty acid content, the temperature should not exceed 40–50 °C [21]. In general, temperatures above 60 °C are undesirable due to the same effect: increased activation energy accelerates oxygen-driven oxidation regardless of the chemical structure of the fatty acids. However, the results of such work (from the 1970s) are currently being ignored by some authors in pursuit of faster experimental turnaround.

Attempts to evaluate correlations between chemical composition and the obtained values revealed the following: shelf life (based on values at 70–100 °C) correlated with the proportion of saturated fatty acids at $r = 0,46$, with monounsaturated fatty acids at $r = 0,45$, and showed an inverse correlation with the proportion of unsaturated fatty acids ($r = -0,52$). However, none of these correlations were statistically significant ($p = 0,11$ to $0,18$). Calculation of the relationship between the values of estimates obtained at temperatures of 50–80 °C and the proportions of fatty acids showed a correlation for saturated fatty acids $r = -0,45$ ($p = 0,2$); monounsaturated fatty acids $0,09$ ($p = 0,7$); and for polyunsaturated fatty acids $r = -0,01$ ($p = 0,9$).

An assessment of the relationship between the estimates obtained at 40–60 °C revealed correlations: for saturated fatty acids, $r = -0,51$ ($p = 0,12$); for monounsaturated fatty acids, $r = -0,62$ ($p = 0,052$); and for polyunsaturated fatty acids, $r = 0,68$ ($p = 0,028$), with the last being statistically significant.

These estimates can be clearly interpreted within the previously proposed paradigm: the oxidation rates of unsaturated fats (with double bonds) and saturated fatty acids converge as temperature increases (i.e., the range between them, Δ , decreases), which undoubtedly distorts the resulting forecasts.

When searching for correlations with individual substances, it was found that the values obtained for the 70–100 °C range correlate with the content of fatty acids with the following carbon skeletons: C:17/0, $r = 0,69$ ($p = 0,027$); C:20/0, $r = 0,92$ ($p = 0,00014$); C:22/0, $r = 0,86$ ($p = 0,001$). For the 40–60 °C range, correlations were found with the concentration of low-chain and unsaturated fatty acids: C:14/0, $r = 0,87$ ($p = 0,0009$); C:16/0, $r = -0,64$ ($p = 0,043$); C:17/0 $r = -0,74$ ($p = 0,012$); C:18/3, $r = 0,71$ ($p = 0,019$).

The values obtained using Tukey's test are also very interesting and are presented in Table 1. As is well known, Tukey's range test provides both statistical values and test power (confidence intervals $1-\alpha$) for any data set. As can be seen from Table 1, when measurements are taken in the 50–80 °C range, the differentiation of the obtained values at the statistical level ($p < 0,05$) is maximal. This holds despite the fact that a correlation of this parameter with the composition and chemical structure of fat components was found for all three categories of fatty acids.

It follows that the parameters and content of fatty acids are adequate for research purposes only in a narrow temperature range. In other cases, excess or insufficient activation energy does not allow reliable estimates (40–60 °C vs. 70–100 °C), which indicates a weakening of the statistical power of these ranges (i.e., differences in storage periods may not be correctly identified).

Table 1
The values of the Tukey's test, for a generalized sample
from literature data and predicted ANN.

T	SFA	MUFA	PUFA
70–100 °C	3,3 (p=0,20)	2,6 (p=0,44)	2,7 (p=0,42)
50–80 °C	7,9 (p=1,10E ⁻⁵)	7,2 (p=5,84E ⁻⁵)	7,3 (p=5,03E ⁻⁵)
40–60 °C	1,54 (p=0,88)	0,88 (p=0,98)	0,94 (p=0,98)

Note: The test shows that the predicted values and chemical composition dependencies are significant for the central temperature range, but not for the remaining ranges, T – temperature; SFA – saturated fatty acids; MUFA – monounsaturated fatty acids; PUFA – polyunsaturated fatty acids.

We calculated the molar mass of a set of glycerol esters and fatty acids (coarsened without taking into account fat-soluble radicals such as chlorophylls or tocopherols). Calculations were performed taking into account the proportions of fatty acids (i.e., as weighted averages). We also estimated the average number of double bonds (C=C) and single carbon-carbon bonds (C-C) per fatty acid molecule, as well as the number of moles of these bonds. Finally, we estimated the activation energy of all these bonds based on the known energy required for a single bond.

Taking into account the molar values and fractions of fatty acids in the indicated oils, the weighted average number of C-C bonds was 16,13 per fatty acid molecule (calculated from the fatty acid composition reported in the literature). This corresponds to approximately three times more moles of these bonds (48,39) per average mole of vegetable oil. The amount of C=C bonds was a weighted average of 0,134 per fatty acid molecule, or 0,402 per mole of triglycerides. If we roughly assume the density of vegetable oils to be 0,914–0,921 g/mL and take into account that the authors used an average of 5 mL per analysis, then the sample mass was 4,57–4,60 g. Given the average molar mass of 279,28 g/mol, this corresponds to 0,0163–0,0165 moles of triglycerides. Based on the previous values, we conclude that 5 mL of oil contains approximately 0,78–0,79 moles of C-C bonds and 0,0066 moles of C=C bonds.

Taking into account the known activation energy of the carbon-carbon bond (without involving mineral or organic catalysts), we calculated the minimum amount of energy required for activation. Based on the literature data, we assume that the C-C bond reaction energy is approximately 90 kcal/mol (377 kJ/mol) [22]. When heated, given the specific heat capacity of iron, the energy transferred is approximately 0,64 kJ/°C/kg of iron (the approximate reactor mass is assumed to be 0,5 kg of iron). We calculated the amount of energy supplied to the sample when heated, for example, to 90 °C: 90 °C × 0,5 kg × 0,64 kJ / °C / kg = 28,8 kJ. At the same time, at least 1,5–3 kJ (taking into account 100% heat dissipation losses) is needed to initiate oxidation of a 0,0165 mol sample. Thus, we apply energy levels to food products that are approximately 10 times higher than the activation energy required for the analysis. It is not surprising that the values between samples «converge» with increasing temperature, because with the given parameters, it does not matter which chemical structure is oxidized – the activation energy for oxygen will be more than sufficient to oxidize any structure.

As additional evidence, we present the IR-Fourier spectral estimates for six types of oils (averaged) that were subjected to heat treatment and stored open at 20 °C indoors for six months. The graph is shown in Figure 4. As shown, the lower graph (shaded in color, corresponding to long-term stored samples) differs markedly from the other two (native oils and samples aged at 90 °C).

Figure 4. IR spectra for the studied oil samples, as well as for samples subjected to accelerated aging and aging in natural conditions at normal temperature for 6 months. Note: the color indicates the spectral characteristics that have changed with natural aging and the types of chemical bonds responsible for this.

In particular, when stored at room temperature, the proportion of molecular groups increases, and their wave characteristics extend the integral area of the broad peak in the 3200–3600 cm^{-1} range, primarily due to peroxide ($-\text{OOH}$) and hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$) groups. Additionally, peroxide and simple ether groups increase the peak area in the 900–1100 cm^{-1} range, which is not observed for hardware - aged oils, since peroxides are thermally unstable.

A similar situation is observed on the graph for the 1200–1300 cm^{-1} range. In contrast, for thermally aged oils, the intensity decreases slightly in the 2800–3000 cm^{-1} range, but more markedly in the 500–600 cm^{-1} range and in the vicinity of 1000 cm^{-1} . This indicates different mechanisms of molecular oxidation. In thermally aged oils, degradation prevails without the formation of peroxides, aldehydes, or esters, whereas during natural aging, all these components accumulate.

This, in theory, allows for the creation of a mathematical apparatus (a computer program) that takes into account not only the shelf life of lipid fractions but also the conditions of such storage. Thus, according to both neural network data and IR Fourier spectrum analysis, excessive temperature (it is recommended not to exceed the average value of 58 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) involves mechanisms different from those of natural aging and is not a direct analogue. This leads to underestimation of the shelf life of food products.

Conclusion. Determining the shelf life of food is an important task directly related to the environmental and technological challenges of incomplete product consumption and subsequent disposal. These factors directly affect emissions and environmental pollution. If the expiration date is set incorrectly or underestimated, it encourages premature disposal of a suitable resource, increasing the mass of food waste in landfills. As is clear from the presented data, temperature ranges of 70–120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ or higher (recommended in some studies) are inappropriate for estimating shelf life. This approach clearly saves time, but it distorts the values obtained during analysis and ultimately leads to a deterioration of the environmental situation.

In our opinion, elevated analysis temperatures (70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and above) are more suitable for determining non-food products, for example, the detonation stability of gasoline fractions of alkanes or cosmetic components. Firstly, gasoline should not contain rapidly oxidizing components, as these would lead to engine destruction upon detonation (ignition would occur prematurely). Secondly, fuel components should not differ significantly from each other in chemical composition — which is not the case for food systems.

In conclusion, we note that the use of machine learning algorithms and modern spectrometry methods has made it possible to identify the existing problem quite elegantly.

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ВЫСОКИЕ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ ПРИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИИ МЕТОДА ASLT ЗАНИЖАЮТ СРОК ГОДНОСТИ ПРОДУКТОВ

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Проблема сроков годности пищевых систем является не только технической, но и глобальной экологической проблемой. Широко применяемый метод ASLT (ускоренное тестирование срока годности) как для продуктов питания, кормов, так и лекарственных средств, требует проверки обоснованности его температурных режимов, в том числе, если речь идет об аппаратных решениях, позволяющих производить автоматизированное прогнозирование сроков хранения. Для проверки адекватности оценок в работе были привлечены как алгоритмы машинного обучения для реанализа опубликованных в литературе данных, так и собственные результаты, полученные с применением ИК-Фурье спектроскопии при полугодовом состаривании образцов. Было показано, что рекомендуемые условия проведения ASLT при температурах 70-100°C и выше, экономят только время проведения анализа, и больше подходят для оценки стабильности непивных образцов (например, бензинов), нежели для продуктов питания.

Ключевые слова: Ускоренное тестирование срока годности (ASLT), занижение значений, ИК-спектроскопия пищевых масел, окисление пищевых продуктов, энергия активации химических реакций (E_a), искусственная нейронная сеть.

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